

Supplemental Table 1. Uniquely identified metabolites from untargeted metabolomics of blood plasma between feed inefficient (LE; n = 8) and efficient (HE; n = 8) mid-lactation multiparous dairy cows enrolled in a 45-day feed efficiency study.

Metabolite	Matched name	HMDB ID	PubChem ID
L-Arginine	L-Arginine	HMDB0000517	6322
L-Tryptophan	L-Tryptophan	HMDB0000929	6305
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phenylalanine	HMDB0000159	6140
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyrosine	HMDB0000158	6057
Glucose 6-phosphate	Glucose 6-phosphate	HMDB0001401	5958
3-methyl pyruvic acid	2-Ketobutyric acid	HMDB0000005	58
Choline	Choline	HMDB0000097	305
L-Leucine	L-Leucine	HMDB0000687	6106
alpha-Santaly acetate	NA	NA	NA
L-Histidine	L-Histidine	HMDB0000177	6274
L-Proline	L-Proline	HMDB0000162	145742
Niacinamide	Niacinamide	HMDB0001406	936
Citric acid	Citric acid	HMDB0000094	311
Citric acid.1	NA	NA	NA
Mannose	D-Mannose	HMDB0000169	18950
L-Valine	L-Valine	HMDB0000883	6287
L-Lactic acid	L-Lactic acid	HMDB0000190	61503
Arachidonic acid	Arachidonic acid	HMDB0001043	444899
Succinic acid semialdehyde	Succinic acid semialdehyde	HMDB0001259	1112
Aniline	Aniline	HMDB0003012	6115
Uridine	Uridine	HMDB0000296	6029
Creatine	Creatine	HMDB0000064	586
Canavanine	Canavanine	HMDB0002706	439202
Isocitric acid	Isocitric acid	HMDB0000193	1198
Isocitric acid.1	NA	NA	NA
Sphingosine	Sphingosine	HMDB0000252	5353955
L-Kynurenine	L-Kynurenine	HMDB0000684	161166
Indolepyruvate	Indolepyruvate	HMDB0060484	803
Uric acid	Uric acid	HMDB0000289	1175
L-Isoleucine	L-Isoleucine	HMDB0000172	6306
Pipecolic acid	Pipecolic acid	HMDB0000070	849
Pipecolic acid.1	NA	NA	NA
5-Aminopentanoic acid	5-Aminopentanoic acid	HMDB0003355	138
Indole	Indole	HMDB0000738	798
Bilirubin	Bilirubin	HMDB0000054	2125225
D-Tryptophan	D-Tryptophan	HMDB0013609	9060
Cyclohexylamine	Cyclohexylamine	HMDB0031404	7965
Gentisic acid	Gentisic acid	HMDB0000152	3469
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	HMDB0011718	126

Cholic acid	Cholic acid	HMDB0000619	221493
Oleic acid	Oleic acid	HMDB0000207	445639
Betaine	Betaine	HMDB0000043	247
Serotonin	Serotonin	HMDB0000259	5202
Creatinine	Creatinine	HMDB0000562	588
Alanyltryptophan	Alanyltryptophan	HMDB0013209	85362
4-Hydroxycinnamic acid	4-Hydroxycinnamic acid	HMDB0002035	637542
D-Glutamine	D-Glutamine	HMDB0003423	145815
p-Cresol	p-Cresol	HMDB0001858	2879
p-Cresol.1	NA	NA	NA
Chalcone	Chalcone	HMDB0003066	637760
Mitobronitol	L-Iditol	HMDB0011632	656655
Stearic acid	Stearic acid	HMDB0000827	5281
2-Furoic acid	2-Furoic acid	HMDB0000617	6919
2-Furoic acid.1	NA	NA	NA
Hippuric acid	Hippuric acid	HMDB0000714	464
Linoleic acid	Linoleic acid	HMDB0000673	5280450
Mesaconic acid	Mesaconic acid	HMDB0000749	643798
Racemethionine	Racemethionine	HMDB0033951	876
But-2-enoic acid	But-2-enoic acid	HMDB0010720	637090
3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-enoic acid	2-Hydroxycinnamic acid	HMDB0002641	637540
4-Oxoproline	4-Oxoproline	METPA0228	NA
Glycocholic acid	Glycocholic acid	HMDB0000138	2361728
L-Norleucine	L-Norleucine	HMDB0001645	21236
Indolelactic acid	Indolelactic acid	HMDB0000671	92904
2-Aminonaphthalene	2-Aminonaphthalene	HMDB0041802	7057
Pyrrolidonecarboxylic acid	Pyrrolidonecarboxylic acid	HMDB0000805	499
Arginine	L-Arginine	HMDB0000517	6322
Beta-Leucine	Beta-Leucine	HMDB0003640	439734
N-Acetylarlyamine	N-Acetylarlyamine	HMDB0001250	904
Dodecanedioic acid	Dodecanedioic acid	HMDB0000623	12736
Triacetate lactone	NA	NA	NA
Propionylcarnitine	Propionylcarnitine	HMDB0000824	107738
Guanidinosuccinic acid	Guanidinosuccinic acid	HMDB0003157	439918
8,11,14-Eicosatrienoic acid	8,11,14-Eicosatrienoic acid	HMDB0002925	5280581
L-threo-3-Phenylserine	L-Threo-3-Phenylserine	HMDB0002184	1231415
Dopamine	Dopamine	HMDB0000073	681
3-Hydroxymethylglutaric acid	3-Hydroxymethylglutaric acid	HMDB0000355	1662
3-Hydroxymethylglutaric acid.1	NA	NA	NA
N6,N6,N6-Trimethyl-L-lysine	N6,N6,N6-Trimethyl-L-lysine	HMDB0001325	440120
Phenylacetylglutamine	Alpha-N-Phenylacetyl-L-glutamine	HMDB0006344	92258
Beta-Tyrosine	Beta-Tyrosine	HMDB0003831	440311
Taurocholic acid	Taurocholic acid	HMDB0000036	6675

Tetrahydrocortisol	Tetrahydrocortisol	HMDB0000949	4472571
Phenylacetylglycine	Phenylacetylglycine	HMDB0000821	68144
5-Hydroxyindoleacetic acid	5-Hydroxyindoleacetic acid	HMDB0000763	1826
5-Hydroxyindoleacetic acid.1	NA	NA	NA
5-Methoxyindoleacetate	5-Methoxyindoleacetate	HMDB0004096	18986
Coumarin	Coumarin	HMDB0001218	323
Pantothenol	Pantothenol	HMDB0004231	4678
Sphingosine 1-phosphate	Sphingosine 1-phosphate	HMDB0000277	5353956
Isoquinoline	Isoquinoline	HMDB0034244	8405
Terephthalic acid	Terephthalic acid	HMDB0002428	7489
2-Quinolone	NA	NA	NA
Quinoline	Quinoline	HMDB0033731	7047
Arachidic acid	Arachidic acid	HMDB0002212	10467
Gamma-Linolenic acid	Gamma-Linolenic acid	HMDB0003073	5280933
Alpha-Linolenic acid	Alpha-Linolenic acid	HMDB0001388	5280934
6-Chloro-N-(1-methylethyl)-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine	6-Chloro-N-(1-methylethyl)-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine	HMDB0033249	22563
6-Chloro-N-(1-methylethyl)-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine.1	NA	NA	NA
4-Sulfocatechol	4-Sulfocatechol	NA	8899
4-Sulfocatechol.1	NA	NA	NA
Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen	HMDB0001859	1983
Acetohydroxamic Acid	Acetohydroxamic Acid	HMDB0014691	1990
Verapamil	Verapamil	HMDB0001850	2520
11b-Hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,17-dione	11b-Hydroxyandrost-4-ene-3,17-dione	HMDB0006773	94141
Methacholine	Methacholine	HMDB0015654	1993
Methacholine.1	NA	NA	NA
Methacholine.2	NA	NA	NA
17a-Ethynylestradiol	17a-Ethynylestradiol	HMDB0001926	5991
Benzphetamine	Benzphetamine	HMDB0015003	5311017
3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine	3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine	HMDB0041931	1614
Salicylic acid	Salicylic acid	HMDB0000840	10253
Salicylic acid.1	NA	NA	NA
2-Quinolone.1	NA	NA	NA
Pirbuterol	Pirbuterol	HMDB0015407	4845
Pirbuterol.1	NA	NA	NA
Butamben	NA	NA	NA
Furazolidone	Furazolidone	HMDB0014752	5323714
Buprenorphine	Buprenorphine	HMDB0015057	644073
Buprenorphine.1	NA	NA	NA
Erythromycin estolate	Erythromycin estolate	NA	441371
3-Methylindole	3-Methylindole	HMDB0000466	6736
alpha-eleostearic acid	alpha-eleostearic acid	NA	5281115

Dihydromethysticin	Dihydromethysticin	HMDB0030791	229852
Arecoline	Arecoline	HMDB0030353	2230
Diethyltoluamide	NA	NA	NA
2-Pyrrolidinone	2-Pyrrolidinone	HMDB0002039	12025
Sodium deoxycholate	Deoxycholic acid	HMDB0000626	222528
Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide	NA	NA	NA
Phytosphingosine	Phytosphingosine	HMDB0004610	122121
Phenolsulfonic acid	NA	NA	NA
Di-n-octyl phthalate	NA	NA	NA
N-Phenyl-1-naphthylamine	NA	NA	NA
N-Phenyl-1-naphthylamine.1	NA	NA	NA
1-Hydroxypyrene	1-Hydroxypyrene	HMDB0013139	5348163
Diisooctyl phthalate	NA	NA	NA
9-OxoODE	9-OxoODE	HMDB0004669	9839084
9-OxoODE.1	NA	NA	NA
12,13-DHOME	12,13-DHOME	HMDB0004705	1023663
D-Carnitine	L-Carnitine	HMDB0000062	2724480
N-Benzylformamide	NA	NA	NA
N-Benzylformamide.1	NA	NA	NA
2,6-diaminohexanoic acid	2,6-diaminohexanoic acid	HMDB0142894	866
Docosapentaenoic acid	Docosapentaenoic acid	HMDB0006528	5497182
16-Hydroxy hexadecanoic acid	16-Hydroxy hexadecanoic acid	HMDB0006294	7058075
16-Hydroxy hexadecanoic acid.1	NA	NA	NA
16-Hydroxy hexadecanoic acid.2	NA	NA	NA
16-Hydroxy hexadecanoic acid.3	NA	NA	NA
Tetraethyl pyrophosphate	NA	NA	NA
Oxyquinoline	NA	NA	NA
1,5-Naphthalenediamine	NA	NA	NA
Hexadecanedioic acid	Hexadecanedioic acid	HMDB0000672	10459
Methyl (indol-3-yl)acetate	NA	NA	NA
Oleylethanolamide	N-Oleylethanolamine	HMDB0002088	5283454

Supplemental Table 1. Differential pathways between inefficient (LE; n = 8) and efficient (HE; n = 8) multiparous dairy cows as determined by pathway enrichment analysis from the 39 differential blood plasma metabolites.

Pathway	Total ¹	Expected ²	Hits ³	Raw P-Value	FDR P-value ⁴
Tryptophan metabolism ⁵	41	0.92	6	<0.01	0.02
Aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis	48	1.07	5	<0.01	0.15
Phenylalanine metabolism	10	0.22	2	0.02	0.55
Glycine, serine, and threonine metabolism	33	0.74	3	0.04	0.74
Biosynthesis of unsaturated fatty acids	36	0.8	3	0.04	0.74
Primary bile acid biosynthesis	46	1.03	3	0.08	1.00
Phenylalanine, tyrosine, and tryptophan biosynthesis	4	0.09	1	0.09	1.00
Valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis	8	0.18	1	0.17	1.00
Taurine and hypotaurine metabolism	8	0.18	1	0.17	1.00
Arginine and proline metabolism	38	0.85	2	0.21	1.00
Arginine biosynthesis	14	0.31	1	0.27	1.00
Nicotinate and nicotinamide metabolism	15	0.34	1	0.29	1.00
Histidine metabolism	16	0.36	1	0.31	1.00
Pantothenate and CoA biosynthesis	19	0.42	1	0.35	1.00
beta-Alanine metabolism	21	0.47	1	0.38	1.00
Pyruvate metabolism	22	0.49	1	0.39	1.00
Glycolysis / Gluconeogenesis	26	0.58	1	0.45	1.00
Porphyrin and chlorophyll metabolism	30	0.67	1	0.50	1.00
Glycerophospholipid metabolism	36	0.8	1	0.56	1.00
Valine, leucine, and isoleucine degradation	40	0.89	1	0.60	1.00
Purine metabolism	65	1.45	1	0.78	1.00
Steroid hormone biosynthesis	85	1.9	1	0.86	1.00

¹Total number of metabolites in the pathway.

²Expected number of metabolites to be different by chance.

³Number of metabolites in the pathway that were different.

⁴False-discovery rate corrected P-value.

⁵Differential metabolites that were numerically greater in LE cows and included in the tryptophan metabolism pathway: L-tryptophan, L-kynurenine, Serotonin, 5-hydroxyindole acetate, and 5-methoxyindole acetate.

Supplemental Table 2. Calculated ingredient composition and nutrient analysis of lactation diets across three replicated mid-lactation feed efficiency studies.

Item, %DM	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	Mean	SE ¹	Mean	SE	Mean	SE
Ingredient composition						
Alfalfa haylage	21.49	1.44	22.26	1.78	20.71	0.49
Corn silage	28.32	1.04	28.23	3.43	26.66	1.44
Distiller's grain	3.44	0.24	1.54	0.06	2.94	0.08
Cottonseed	4.70	0.23	4.87	0.22	4.88	0.17
High Moisture Corn	13.45	0.84	14.79	2.14	16.12	0.85
Protein concentration mix ²	28.59	0.69	28.31	1.01	28.70	0.43
Nutrient analysis						
DM, % as fed	53.20		51.02		52.56	
OM	93.86		93.00		92.28	
CP	17.29		18.15		16.94	
NDF	29.34		30.77		25.49	
NDFom	28.40		29.63		24.36	
ADF	21.84		22.11		17.84	
Lignin	3.40		3.06		2.93	
NFC	43.02		40.00		44.96	
Starch	25.54		24.97		29.57	
Fat	4.21		4.08		4.89	
NEL 3x, Mcal/kg DM	1.65		1.63		1.68	

¹SE= Standard error of the mean.

²Protein concentration mix was formulated to contain (% as-fed) fine ground corn (25.09%), canola meal (28.96%), soy hull pellet (17.60%), 42% CP exceller meal (12.73%), 46% CP soybean meal (4.99%), calcium carbonate (4.49%), sodium bicarbonate (2.50%), trace mineral salt (1.25%), grease (0.25%, Sanimax, Green Bay, WI), magnesium oxide (0.75%), urea (0.62%), potassium carbonate (0.30%), DynaMate (0.15%, The Mosaic Company, Plymouth, MN), Smartamine M (0.15%, Adisseo, Alpharetta, GA), and Fortress LG (0.16%, VitaPlus, Madison, WI).